

(1, 2)*-GENERALIZED η -CLOSED SETS IN BITOPOLOGICAL SPACES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we introduce (1, 2)*-generalized η -closed sets and obtain the relationships among some existing closed sets like (1, 2)*-semi-closed, (1, 2)*- α -closed and (1, 2)*- η -closed sets and their generalizations. Also we study some basic properties of (1, 2)*- $g\eta$ -open sets. Further, we introduce (1, 2)*- $g\eta$ -neighbourhood and discuss some properties of (1, 2)*- $g\eta$ -neighbourhood.

1. Introduction

The study of bitopological spaces was first initiated by Kelly [4] in the year 1963. By using the topological notions, namely, semi-open, α -open and pre-open sets, many new bitopological sets are defined and studied by many topologists. In 2008, Ravi et al. [6] studied the notion of (1, 2)*-sets in bitopological spaces. In 2004, Ravi and Thivagar [5] studied the concept of stronger form of (1, 2)*-quotient mapping in bitopological spaces and introduced the concepts of (1, 2)*-semi-open and (1, 2)*- α -open sets in bitopological spaces. Recently H. Kumar [3] introduced the concept of (1, 2)*- η -open sets and discuss their properties.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout the paper $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$, (Y, σ_1, σ_2) and (Z, \wp_1, \wp_2) (or simply X , Y and Z) denote bitopological spaces.

Definition 2.1. Let S be a subset of X . Then S is said to be $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open [5] if $S = A \cup B$ where $A \in \mathfrak{T}_1$ and $B \in \mathfrak{T}_2$. The complement of a $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open set is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed.

Definition 2.2 [5]. Let S be a subset of X . Then

(i) the $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closure of S , denoted by $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(S)$, is defined as $\bigcap \{F : S \subset F \text{ and } F \text{ is } \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-closed}\}$; (ii) the $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -interior of S , denoted by $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(S)$, is defined as $\bigcup \{F : F \subset S \text{ and } F \text{ is } \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-open}\}$.

Note 2.3 [5]. Notice that $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open sets need not necessarily form a topology.

Remark 2.4. [6]

(i) $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(S)$ is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open for each $S \subset X$ and $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(S)$ is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed for each $S \subset X$.

(ii) A subset $S \subset X$ is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open iff $S = \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(S)$ and $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed iff $S = \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(S)$.

(iii) $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(S) = \mathfrak{T}_1\text{-int}(S) \cup \mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(S)$ and $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(S) = \mathfrak{T}_1\text{-cl}(S) \cup \mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(S)$ for any $S \subset X$.

(iv) for any family $\{S_i / i \in I\}$ of subsets of X , we have

- (1) $\cup_i \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(S_i) \subset \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(\cup_i S_i)$.
- (2) $\cup_i \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(S_i) \subset \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\cup_i S_i)$.
- (3) $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(\cup_i S_i) \subset \cup_i S_i \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(S_i)$.
- (4) $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\cup_i S_i) \subset \cup_i \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(S_i)$.

Definition 2.5. A subset A of a bitopological space $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is called

- (i) $(1, 2)^*$ -**semi-open** [5] if $A = \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(A))$,
- (ii) $(1, 2)^*$ - **α -open** [5] if $A \subset \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(A)))$.
- (iii) $(1, 2)^*$ - **η -open** [5] if $A \subset \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(A)) \cup \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(A)))$.

The complement of a $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open, $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open) set is called **$(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed** (resp. **$(1, 2)^*$ - α -closed**, **$(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed**).

The **$(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closure** (resp. **$(1, 2)^*$ - α -closure**, **$(1, 2)^*$ - η -closure**) of a subset A of X is denoted by **$(1, 2)^*$ -s-cl(A)** (resp. **$(1, 2)^*$ - α -cl(A)**, **$(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A)**), defined as the intersection of all $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed. (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed) sets containing A .

The family of all $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open, $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open, $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed) sets in X is denoted by $(1, 2)^*$ -SO(X) (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ - α O(X), $(1, 2)^*$ - η O(X), $(1, 2)^*$ -SC(X), $(1, 2)^*$ - α C(X), $(1, 2)^*$ - η C(X)).

Remark 2.6. It is evident that any $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open set of X is an $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open and each $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open set of X is $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open but the converses are not true.

Remark 2.7. We have the following implications for the properties of subsets [3]:

$$\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-open} \Rightarrow (1, 2)^*\text{-}\alpha\text{-open} \Rightarrow (1, 2)^*\text{-semi-open} \Rightarrow (1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-open}$$

Where none of the implications is reversible.

3. $(1, 2)^*$ -generalized η -closed Sets in Bitopological Spaces

Definition 3.1. A subset A of a bitopological space $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is called

- (i) $(1, 2)^*$ -generalized closed (briefly $(1, 2)^*$ -g-closed) [8] if $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open in X .
- (ii) $(1, 2)^*$ -weakly closed (briefly $(1, 2)^*$ -w-closed) [2] if $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open in X .
- (iii) $(1, 2)^*$ - α -generalized closed (briefly $(1, 2)^*$ - α g-closed) [8] if $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open in X .
- (iv) $(1, 2)^*$ -generalized semi-closed (briefly $(1, 2)^*$ -gs-closed) [8] if $(1, 2)^*\text{-s-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open in X .
- (v) $(1, 2)^*$ -generalized η -closed (briefly $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed) if $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open in X .

The complement of a $(1, 2)^*$ -g-closed (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ -w-closed, $(1, 2)^*$ -ag-closed, $(1, 2)^*$ -gs-closed, $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed) set is called $(1, 2)^*$ -g-open (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ -w-open, $(1, 2)^*$ -ag-open, $(1, 2)^*$ -gs-open, $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -open). We denote the set of all $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed sets in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ by $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -C(X).

Theorem 3.2. Every $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed set is g η -closed.

Proof. Let A be any $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ and $A \subset U$, where U is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open. So $(1, 2)^*$ -cl(A) = A. Since every $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed set is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed, so $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset $(1, 2)^*$ -cl(A) = A. Therefore, $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset A \subset U. Hence A is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed set.

Theorem 3.3. Every $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closed set is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed.

Proof. Let A be any $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closed set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ and $A \subset U$, where U is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open. Since every $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closed set is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed, so $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset $(1, 2)^*$ - α -cl(A) = A. Therefore $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset A \subset U. Hence A is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed set.

Theorem 3.4. Every $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed set is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed.

Proof. Let A be any $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ and $A \subset U$, where U is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open. Since every $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed set is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed, so $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset $(1, 2)^*$ -s-cl(A) = A. Therefore $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset A \subset U. Hence A is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed set.

Theorem 3.5. Every $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed set is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed.

Proof. Let A be any $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ and $A \subset U$, where U is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open. Since A is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed. Therefore $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) = A \subset U. Hence A is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed set.

Theorem 3.6. Every $(1, 2)^*$ -g-closed set is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed.

Proof. Let A be any $(1, 2)^*$ -g-closed set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ then $(1, 2)^*$ -cl(A) \subset U whenever $A \subset U$, where U is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open. So $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset $(1, 2)^*$ -cl(A) \subset U. Therefore $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset U. Hence A is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed set.

Theorem 3.7. Every $(1, 2)^*$ -w-closed set is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed.

Proof. Let A be any $(1, 2)^*$ -w-closed set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ then $(1, 2)^*$ -cl(A) \subset U whenever $A \subset U$, where U is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open, since every $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open set is $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open. So $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset $(1, 2)^*$ -cl(A) \subset U. Therefore $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset U. Hence A is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed set.

Theorem 3.8. Every $(1, 2)^*$ -ag-closed set is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed.

Proof. Let A be any $(1, 2)^*$ -ag-closed set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ then $(1, 2)^*$ - α -cl(A) \subset U whenever $A \subset U$, where U is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open. Given that A is $(1, 2)^*$ -ag-closed set such that $(1, 2)^*$ - α -cl(A) \subset U. But we have $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset $(1, 2)^*$ - α -cl(A) \subset U. Therefore $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset U. Hence A is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed set.

Theorem 3.9. Every $(1, 2)^*$ -gs-closed set is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed.

Proof. Let A be any $(1, 2)^*$ -gs-closed set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ then $(1, 2)^*$ -s-cl(A) \subset U whenever $A \subset U$, where U is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open. Given that A is $(1, 2)^*$ -gs-closed set such that $(1, 2)^*$ -s-cl(A) \subset U. But we have $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset $(1, 2)^*$ -s-cl(A) \subset U. Therefore $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A) \subset U. Hence A is $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed set.

Remark 3.10. We have the following implications for the properties of subsets:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

Example 3.11. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$. Then

- (i) $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (ii) $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (iii) $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (iv) $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (v) $(1, 2)^*$ -g-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (vi) $(1, 2)^*$ -w-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (vii) $(1, 2)^*$ - α g-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (viii) $(1, 2)^*$ -gs-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (ix) $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

Example 3.12. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{b\}\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{c\}\}$. Then

- (i) $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$.
- (ii) $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$.
- (iii) $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$.
- (iv) $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$.
- (v) $(1, 2)^*$ -g-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$.
- (vi) $(1, 2)^*$ -w-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$.
- (vii) $(1, 2)^*$ - α g-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$.
- (viii) $(1, 2)^*$ -gs-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$.
- (ix) $(1, 2)^*$ -g η -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$.

Example 3.13. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Then

- (i) $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (ii) $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (iii) $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (iv) $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (v) $(1, 2)^*$ -g-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (vi) $(1, 2)^*$ -w-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (vii) $(1, 2)^*$ - α g-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (viii) $(1, 2)^*$ -gs-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (ix) $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

Example 3.14. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{a, b, d\}\}$. Then

- (i) $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (ii) $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (iii) $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (iv) $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (v) $(1, 2)^*$ -g-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (vi) $(1, 2)^*$ -w-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (vii) $(1, 2)^*$ - α g-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (viii) $(1, 2)^*$ -gs-closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (ix) $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed sets : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

4. Some Properties of $(1, 2)^*$ -generalized η -closed Sets

Theorem 4.1. The union of any two $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed subsets of $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is need not be $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed subset of $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ as per the following example.

Example 4.2. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Here $A = \{a\}$ and $B = \{b\}$ are $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed subsets in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. Then $A \cup B = \{a, b\}$ is not $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed subsets in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$.

Remark 4.3. The intersection of two $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed-sets in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is also a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$.

Proof. Easy to verify.

Theorem 4.4. If a subset A is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed of X , then $(1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A) - A$ does not contain any non-empty $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed set.

Proof. Let F be a $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed subset of $(1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A) - A$. Then $F \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A)$ and $F \cap A = \emptyset$. Therefore $X - F$ is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open and hence $X - F$ is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open. Since $F \cap A = \emptyset$, $A \subset X - F$. But A is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed, then $(1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A) \subset X - F$ and consequently $F \subset X - (1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A)$. Therefore $F \subset ((1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A)) \cap (X - (1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A))$ and hence F is empty.

Remark 4.5. The converse of **Theorem 4.4** is not true as per the following example.

Example 4.6. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ with $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\emptyset, X, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c, d\}\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\emptyset, X, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c, d\}\}$. If we consider $A = \{a, c\}$, then $(1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A) - A = X - \{a, c\} = \{b, c\}$ does not contain any non-empty $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed set. However A is not $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed.

Theorem 4.7. Let A be a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed subset of X . If $A \subset B \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A)$, then B is also $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed in X .

Proof. Let $U \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta\text{O}(X)$ with $B \subset U$. Then $A \subset U$. Since A is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$. Also, since $B \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A)$, $(1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(B) \subset (1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$. Hence B is also $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed subset of X .

Theorem 4.8. For an element $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$, the set $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2) - \{x\}$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed or $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open.

Proof. Suppose $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2) - \{x\}$ is not $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open set. Then $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is the only $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open set containing $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2) - \{x\}$. This implies $(1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}((X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2) - \{x\}) \subset (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. Hence $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2) - \{x\}$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$.

Theorem 4.9. If A is an open and S is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open in bitopological space $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$, then $A \cap S$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$.

Theorem 4.10. If A is both open and $(1, 2)^*$ - g -closed set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$, then it is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$.

Proof. Let A be an open and $(1, 2)^*$ - g -closed set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. Let $A \subset U$ and let U be a $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open set in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. Now $A \subset A$. By hypothesis $(1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A) \subset A$. That is $(1, 2)^*$ - η - $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$. Thus A is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$.

5. $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open sets and $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -neighborhood

In this section, we study $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open sets in bitopological spaces and obtain some of their properties. Also, we introduce $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -neighborhood (shortly $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd in bitopological spaces by using the notion of $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open sets. We prove that every nbhd of x in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of x but not conversely.

Definition 5.1. A subset A in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is called $(1, 2)^*$ -generalized η -open (briefly, $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open) in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ if A^c is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -closed in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. We denote the family of all $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open sets in X by $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta\text{O}(X)$.

Definition 5.2. Let $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ be a bitopological space and let $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. A subset N of $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is said to be a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of x iff there exists a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set G such that $x \in G \subset N$.

Definition 5.3. A subset N of a bitopological space $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$, is called a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of $A \subset (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ iff there exists a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set G such that $A \subset G \subset N$.

Remark 5.4. The $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd N of $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ need not be a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$.

Example 5.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, X\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta O(X) = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, e\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, \{c, d, e\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, \{a, b, c, e\}, \{a, b, d, e\}, \{a, c, d, e\}, \{b, c, d, e\}\}$. Note that $\{a, e\}$ is not a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set, but it is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of a , since $\{a\}$ is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set such that $a \in \{a\} \subset \{a, e\}$.

Theorem 5.6. Every nbhd N of $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$.

Proof. Let N be a nbhd of point $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. To prove that N is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of x . By definition of nbhd, there exists an open set G such that $x \in G \subset N$. As every open set is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set G such that $x \in G \subset N$. Hence N is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of x .

Remark 5.7. In general, a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd N of $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ need not be a nbhd of x in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$, as seen from the following example.

Example 5.8. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with topology $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Then $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta O(X) = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$. The set $\{b, c\}$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of the point b , there exists an $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set $\{b\}$ is such that $b \in \{b\} \subset \{b, c\}$. However, the set $\{b, c\}$ is not a nbhd of the point b , since no open set G exists such that $b \in G \subset \{a, c\}$.

Theorem 5.9. If a subset N of a space $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open, then N is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of each of its points.

Proof. Suppose N is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open. Let $x \in N$. We claim that N is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of x . For N is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set such that $x \in N \subset N$. Since x is an arbitrary point of N , it follows that N is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of each of its points.

Remark 5.10. The converse of the above theorem is not true in general as seen from the following example.

Example 5.11. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ with topology $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, X\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Then $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta O(X) = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, e\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, \{c, d, e\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, \{a, b, c, e\}, \{a, b, d, e\}, \{a, c, d, e\}, \{b, c, d, e\}\}$. The set $\{a, b, c\}$ is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of the points a, b and c since the $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open sets $\{a\}, \{b\}$ and $\{c\}$ for the points a, b and c respectively, such that $a \in \{a\} \subset \{a, b, c\}$; $b \in \{b\} \subset \{a, b, c\}$ and $c \in \{c\} \subset \{a, b, c\}$ respectively. That is $\{a, b, c\}$ is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of each of its points. However the set $\{a, b, c\}$ is not a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set in X .

Definition 5.12. Let x be a point in a space $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. The set of all $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of x is called the **$(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd system** at x , and is denoted by $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$.

Theorem 5.13. Let $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ be a bitopological space and for each $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. Let $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$ be the collection of all $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhds of x . Then we have the following results.

- (i) $\forall x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$, $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x) \neq \phi$.
- (ii) $N \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x) \Rightarrow x \in N$.
- (iii) $N \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$, $M \supset N \Rightarrow M \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$.
- (iv) $N \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$, $M \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x) \Rightarrow N \cap M \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$.
- (v) $N \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x) \Rightarrow$ there exists $M \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$ such that $M \subset N$ and $M \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(y)$ for every $y \in M$.

Proof. (i) Since $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set, it is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of every $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. Hence there exists at least one $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd (namely - $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$) for each $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. Hence $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x) = \phi$ for every $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$.

(ii) If $N \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$, then N is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of x . So by definition of $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd, $x \in N$.

(iii) Let $N \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$ and $M \supset N$. Then there is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set G such that $x \in G \subset N$. Since $N \subset M$, $x \in G \subset M$ and so M is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of x . Hence $M \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$.

(iv) Let $N \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$ and $M \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$. Then by definition of $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd. Hence $x \in G_1 \cap G_2 \subset N \cap M \Rightarrow (1)$. Since $G_1 \cap G_2$ is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set, (being the intersection of two $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open sets), it follows from (1) that $N \cap M$ is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of x . Hence $N \cap M \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$.

(v) If $N \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(x)$, then there exists a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set M such that $x \in M \subset N$. Since M is a $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -open set, it is $(1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ -nbhd of each of its points. Therefore $M \in (1, 2)^*$ - $g\eta$ - $N(y)$ for every $y \in M$.

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